

Results: In close contact with the local responsible authorities, the project findings will be used to recommend policy options - technological and non-technological - to control air pollution and to reduce the carbon footprint of European cities in the short and medium term (up to 2030). For the long-term perspective (2050 and later), it will develop green city models - future visions - and explore the pathways of participating cities towards more sustainable and healthy environments.

Conclusions/Recommendations: ICARUS conclusions will be translated into a web-based guidebook for sustainable air pollution and climate change governance in all EU cities.

Funding: ICARUS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 690105. This work reflects only the authors' views and that the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. <http://icarus2020.eu>

CP18. Salud ambiental y laboral/Saúde ambiental e trabalhista

Jueves, 13 de septiembre de 2018. 15:00-17:00
Pantalla 3

Moderan: Pablo Sánchez Villegas

338. ICARUS PROJECT: INTEGRATED CLIMATE FORCING AND AIR POLLUTION REDUCTION IN URBAN SYSTEMS

R. Izquierdo, R. Ramis, R. Franco, J. Soria-Lara, D. Sarigiannis, A. Gotti, S. García dos Santos-Alves, E. Boldo, on behalf of the ICARUS network

CNE-ISCI; CNSA-ISCI; IDIPHIM; CIBERESP; UPM; AUTH.

Background/Objectives: Air pollutant concentrations are still above the legal and recommended limits that are set to protect the health of European citizens. Improvements in air quality would result in significant health gains, mainly in European urban settlement. Understanding the effectiveness of urban air pollution control policies is important to promote development-oriented air quality policies. ICARUS project will assess the impact of national and local policies on reducing greenhouse gas emissions and improving air quality, and will evaluate the future public health and wellbeing impacts of these policies in European cities.

Methods: ICARUS is a four-year project (2016-2020), and the network involves a multidisciplinary expertise in the environment, climate and public health from 18 partners institutions associated in 9 European countries. The methodology will be applied in nine European cities of variable size starting from relatively small (Basel, Brno, Ljubljana) to mid-size (Stuttgart, Bristol, Thessaloniki) to large cities (Athens, Milan and Madrid), and with different socioeconomic status and history. ICARUS will develop tools and strategies to assess the impact of key sectoral policies on improving air quality, mitigating climate change and promoting health. On the one hand, an integrated approach will be used for air pollution monitoring, combining ground-based measurements, atmospheric transport and chemistry modelling as well as air pollution indicators. On the other hand, modelling tools will be used to estimate population exposure, taking into account socio-economic status differences. Finally, health impact assessment will consider feasible policy options to support cost-effectiveness and cost-benefit analysis.